

A review on machine learning approaches for microalgae cultivation systems

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ABSTRACT

Microalgae plays a crucial role in biomass production within aquatic environments and are increasingly recognized for their potential in generating biofuels, biomaterials, bioactive compounds, and bio-based chemicals. This growing significance is driven by the need to address imminent global challenges such as food and fuel shortages. Enhancing the value chain of bio-based products necessitates the implementation of an advanced screening and monitoring system. This system is crucial for tailoring and optimizing the cultivation conditions, ensuring the lucrative and efficient production of the final desired product. This, in turn, underscores the necessity for robust predictive models to accurately emulate algae growth in different conditions during the initial cultivation phase and simulate their subsequent processing in the downstream stage. In pursuit of these objectives, diverse mechanistic and machine learning-based methods have been independently employed to model and optimize microalgae processes. This review article thoroughly examines the techniques delineated in the literature for modeling, predicting, and monitoring microalgal biomass across various applications such as bioenergy, pharmaceuticals, and the food industry. While highlighting the merits and limitations of each method, we delve into the realm of newly emerging hybrid approaches and conduct an exhaustive survey of this evolving methodology. The challenges currently impeding the practical implementation of hybrid techniques are explored, and drawing inspiration from successful applications in other machine-learning-assisted fields, we review various plausible solutions to overcome these obstacles.

1. Introduction

Phototrophic microorganisms such as cyanobacteria and microalgae are an important renewable resource for the future and the basis for various industrial sectors [1]. The production of biomass is based on photosynthesis by using light as energy and CO₂ as a carbon source. In addition, the huge number of phototrophic species provides the basis for using different water sources, such as freshwater, brackish water, seawater, or (industrial) wastewater [2]. A variety of products can be derived from the biomass produced, either by utilizing the entire biomass as food/feed or by extracting cell components, such as pigments, proteins, carbohydrates, and fats in a biorefinery approach [3]. Microalgae are a rich source of minerals, vitamins, amino acids, and antioxidants, and they also have a sugar-lowering effect rendering them suitable for use in medicine, cosmetics, sports, animal husbandry, beekeeping, as well as fish and poultry farming [4–6].

The extensive use of fossil fuels in energy generation has become a significant contributor to global warming. As a potential solution,

microalgae have garnered attention as an alternative energy source for producing various biofuels, including biodiesel, biohydrogen, bioethanol, bio-oil, and biogas. This approach holds promise in addressing the challenges posed by global warming due to its inherent carbon-neutral or carbon-balanced nature [7–9]. Furthermore, microalgae exhibit superior rates of bio-oil production and photosynthetic efficiency compared to other plant species. These attributes make microalgae a highly desirable option for sustainable energy production, offering enhanced yields and optimized resource utilization [7–9]. The overview of the microalgae cultivation process for producing different products is presented in Fig. 1.

In addition to the energetic utilization, microalgae are also a source of numerous health-promoting metabolites, such as anti-inflammatory carotenoids [10] or omega-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (LC-PUFAs). Studies have shown that bioactive LC-PUFAs, namely eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), can help

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Fig. 1. Microalgae cultivation principle, downstream processing with different bioproducts obtained.

treat neurological disorders, cardiovascular diseases, and even several types of cancers [11–21]. Fishes and shellfishes are the natural sources of LC-PUFAs. However, due to the problems of overfishing and global warming, researchers are interested in finding alternative sources for producing LC-PUFAs. Microalgae are cultivated in photobioreactors (PBR) — classified in open cultivation systems, such as open ponds, tanks, raceway ponds, and closed cultivation systems. In general, open cultivation systems have lower investment costs but show limitations in biomass productivity and process quality in terms of contamination control and water evaporation compared to closed cultivation systems [22].

Algae cultivation process, like other bioprocesses, is highly complex because they are impacted by the technical system characteristics, such as geometry and power input, as well as the kinetic properties of photosynthesis and the growth kinetics of the microorganisms, which are mainly triggered by light intensity, pH, salinity, nutrition availability, temperature, CO₂, and dissolved oxygen content. The biomass productivity can be increased by optimizing these culture conditions using physics-based, data-driven, or hybrid models [23]. Among physics-based models, kinetic models are commonly used to improve the PBR performance [24]. The kinetic models based on traditional models like Monod, Droop, and Logistic models [25] are extensively used in modern industries owing to their data-fitting capabilities across a broad range of bioprocesses. While kinetic models excel at fitting available data, their predictive accuracy is often limited when applied to complex biological systems like algal photo-production. This limitation stems from their structural constraints, as these models attempt to consolidate numerous metabolic pathways into a simplified framework, aggregating vast amounts of information into a few parameters. Consequently, this oversimplified representation may fail to capture the nuanced interactions and dynamics inherent in these intricate systems [26,27]. Data-driven models have been proposed in the literature as alternatives to kinetic models, primarily due to their capacity to incorporate a broader array of parameters and structural complexities for data regression. They also capture the varied process behaviors accumulated at multiple operating conditions in a single model [28]. Different machine learning (ML) models, such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), Decision Trees (DT), Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting (GB), Multilayer perceptron (MLP), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) have been used to enhance long-term semi-continuous processes and optimize the culture conditions for achieving higher PBR productivity [29–31]. This review outlines the importance of using ML techniques including deep learning to optimize

various culture conditions for achieving higher growth and productivity of microalgae. This review article also discusses how hybrid modeling approaches can be used as an alternative strategy for predicting, modeling, and optimizing microalgae processes.

2. Methodology

The ultimate target publications were those that focus on the prediction of microalgae growth by analyzing various factors such as light, temperature, nutrients, and pH as well as its downstream processing using ML algorithms. The identification of studies involved searches in electronic databases, specifically Science Direct and Google Scholar. The most recent search was performed on January 19, 2024. The following keywords were utilized in this review: “Algal biomass”, “Photobioreactor”, “Regression”, and “Downstream processing”. Additionally, we excluded the following terms: “Classification”, “Wastewater”, “Bio-gas”, “Bio-fuel”, and “Bio-diesel”. Most of the search results were restricted to the period from 2017 to 2024. We screened the abstracts before thoroughly reading the chosen studies to excerpt only the abovementioned target publications, which include 125 publications. Fig. 2 depicts the distribution of studies over the years, showing the increasing popularity of this research topic since 1988.

3. Overview of ML approaches

Various neural-network-based and non-neural-network-based ML algorithms have been proposed in the literature for the growth prediction and downstream of microalgal processes, and this section provides an overview of the most commonly used neural-network-based and non-neural-network-based ML algorithms as shown in Fig. 3. Moreover, we summarize ML models utilized for various purposes: classification, regression, anomaly detection, and time-series analysis within microalgae production, as outlined in Table 1. Nonetheless, the primary focus of this article centers on predicting and monitoring microalgae processes.

3.1. Non-neural-network-based ML approaches

This section overviews non-neural network-based ML approaches used for predicting microalgae processes.

Linear regression is a well-known regression method as well as one of the most popular ML modeling techniques. This method uses a continuous dependent variable, independent variables can be continuous or discrete, and a type of regression line is linear. Linear regression

Fig. 2. Number of articles reviewed in this survey.

Fig. 3. Machine-Learning approaches for microalgae production and processing.

Table 1
The taxonomy of different ML methods for microalgae production.

Microalgae production tasks	ML tasks	ML models	References
Strain selection	Classification	Decision trees, Support vector machines	[32,33]
Growth rate prediction	Regression	Linear regression, Random forest, Long short-term memory	[34,35]
Nutrient optimization	Optimization	Reinforcement learning	[36]
Contamination detection	Anomaly detection	Autoencoders, One-class support vector machines	[37]
Harvesting automation	Robotics	Computer vision, Reinforcement learning	[38]
Environmental monitoring	Time series analysis	ARIMA, Long short-term memory, Gated recurrent units	[39,40]

forms a connection between the dependent variable and one or more independent variables (also known as a regression line) employing the best-fit straight line [41]. Multiple linear regression is a modification of basic linear regression that permits more than one variable to model an output variable, y , as a linear function [41]; on the other hand, simple linear regression requires only one independent variable.

Another standard method used in ML is the support vector machine (SVM), which can be used for regression and classification tasks [42]. An SVM generates a hyper-plane or a group of hyper-planes in high-

infinite-dimensional space. It performs effectively in high-dimensional spaces and exhibits different behavior depending on the various mathematical functions known as kernels. The most common kernels in SVM are linear, polynomial, radial basis function (RBF), and sigmoid [43].

Decision tree (DT) [44] is a renowned non-parametric supervised learning technique that is used for classification and regression tasks [43]. DT categorizes the instances by arranging the tree from the root to a particular leaf node. Instances are categorized by examining the

attribute described by that node, beginning at the tree's root node and moving along the tree branch corresponding to the attribute value.

The ensemble classification approach, often known as a random forest (RF) classifier [45], is widely used in ML and data science for various applications. It may be utilized for classification and regression issues and adapts well to categorical and continuous inputs. This technique uses "parallel ensembling", which entails parallel-fitting several decision tree classifiers on different dataset sub-samples and determining the results through average or majority vote. As a result, over-fitting is reduced, and prediction performance and control are improved [43]. RF learning models based on many decision trees are frequently more accurate than models based on a single decision tree [46].

Similar to Random Forests [45], as discussed above, Extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) is an ensemble learning algorithm that constructs a final model from several individual models, commonly decision trees. XGBoost is a type of gradient boosting; that considers more accurate approximations when identifying the optimal model [43]. It calculates advanced regularization (L1 and L2) [43] and second-order gradients of the loss function to minimize the loss that reduces over-fitting and enhances model generalization and performance.

Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) is a linear decision boundary classifier constructed by fitting class-dependent densities to data and applying Bayes' rule [43,47]. This technique also referred to as a generalization of Fisher's linear discriminant, reduces the dimensionality of the space in which a dataset is projected, thus minimizing the model's complexity or lowering the processing costs of the resulting model. ANOVA (analysis of variance) and regression analysis, which aim to represent one dependent variable as a linear combination of other features or measurements, are closely connected to LDA.

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) [48] is a supervised learning algorithm that can be used for classification and regression tasks. Based on similarity metrics such as the Euclidean distance function, KNN classifies new data points using existing data. The KNN's accuracy depends on the data quality and is resilient to noisy training data. The major challenge associated with KNN is determining the optimal number of neighbors [49].

Stochastic gradient descent (SGD) [41] is a repetitive process for optimizing a loss function with appropriate smoothness properties, where the term 'stochastic' directs to random probability. This lessens the computational cost, specifically for high-dimensional optimization issues, that permits more rapid repetitions in exchange for a lower convergence rate. The slope of a function used to determine a variable's degree of change in response to another variable's changes is known as the gradient. The Gradient Descent is a convex function mathematically that generates a partial derivative of a set of input parameters.

3.2. Neural-network-based ML approaches

A multilayer perceptron (MLP) is the basic structure of deep learning, sometimes called the feed-forward artificial neural network [43]. A standard MLP is a fully connected network that consists of an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer. At a specific weight, each node in one layer connects to each node in the subsequent layer. MLP adjusts the weight values internally while creating the model using the "Backpropagation" approach [41], the most "basic structure" in a neural network. The number of hidden layers, neurons, and iterations are only a few of the hyperparameters to be tuned in MLP, which is sensitive to scaling features and can lead to a computationally expensive model. The standard ANN, which consists of fully connected, pooling, and convolutional layers, is enhanced by CNN [50].

It is frequently widely used in various fields, including video and image recognition, image processing and classification, medical image analysis, and natural language processing because it takes advantage of the two-dimensional structure of the input data. CNN requires more processing and higher computational cost; it has the advantage of

automatically identifying the key features, which makes it more powerful than traditional ANNs. Long short-term memory (LSTM) is an artificial neural network (ANN) architecture used in the field of artificial intelligence (AI), and deep learning [51]. In contrast to standard feed-forward neural networks (FFNN), LSTM has feedback connections. LSTM networks differ from conventional networks because they are effective at analyzing and learning sequential data, including classifying, processing, and making predictions based on time series data. Therefore, LSTM can be employed for sequential data, such as time series, and is typically used in natural language processing, time-series analysis, and speech recognition.

4. ML approaches to enhance microalgae growth and productivity

Due to various complicated metabolic reactions inside a cell, it is very challenging to model a bioprocess. For instance, several factors contribute to the development of metabolic-engineered products. The complex medium's compositions, the cell line's source, and biochemical pathways are significant [52], and these biochemical reactions are typically expressed mathematically as nonlinear and time-varying functions. Furthermore, Glacken et al. has employed simplified first-principles models to exemplify hybridoma culture kinetics. The authors have proposed several structured models for intracellular metabolism to illustrate microorganism growth and product formation [54]. The derived equations are a simplified form of biochemical conversions inside the cell and do not comprehensively explain the aspects that influence chemical and physical processes [55]. Due to these complex biological models, various ML methods including deep neural network approaches have appeared as an optimistic approach for modeling and optimizing bioprocesses [56].

4.1. Prediction of microalgae growth or productivity using neural-network-based and non-neural-network-based approaches

Coşgun et al. has used the ML algorithm to predict the algal biomass productivity and lipid content. This study initially investigated the influential parameters, including microalgae species, cultivation conditions, reactor type, nutrient concentration, stress conditions, cell disruption methods, light intensity, CO₂ quantity, and lipid extraction solvents on biomass and lipid production. Additionally, the dataset has been processed using ML approaches such as the decision tree and the association rule. A decision tree model has been used to identify the variables that led to high biomass and lipid content; on the other hand, association rule mining has been used to find the actual circumstances that contributed to higher biomass and lipid levels. For the decision tree analysis, the median lipid content (20%) has been employed as the upper limit for high lipid content.

Two-thirds of the data has randomly been taken as the training set, while the remaining one-third has been utilized for validation, as in the case of biomass productivity. The decision tree developed in their study used MaxNumSplits = 30 and MinLeafSize = 2. According to split criteria, their study has analyzed that Gini's diversity index has attained better performance than the "towing rule" and the "maximum deviance reduction". The decision tree has achieved high lipid content in microalgae cells due to the conditions explained above; then, association rule mining has been employed as a different approach to obtain more specific information about the most relevant factors. For the association rule model, again, the datasets have been split into three groups, such as deficient [0%, 10%), medium [10 %, 30 %), and higher [30 %, 74.8%]. Due to such data division, this study has investigated the most influential parameters contributing to higher biomass and lipid content. The study of Ambat et al. has statistically investigated the correlation between biomass production and lipid productivity in various wastewater sources. By cultivating different algal biomass in several types of wastewater effluent, the linear regression approach

with Monte Carlo simulation has been employed to predict total nitrogen (TN), total phosphorus (TP), chemical oxygen demand (COD), and CO₂ sequestration. The R^2 score of COD, TP, TN, CO₂ versus biomass production, and biomass production versus CO₂ fixation using various microalgal species have been reported below (Table 2).

Lopez-Exposito et al. has employed an innovative strategy for floc length and geometric shape during the growth of microalgae in a random forest regression model to decrease the cost of microalgae harvesting. The optimized hyperparameters have been used for the RF model, such as the number of trees, maximum depth, the minimum number of samples allowed, and the maximum number of features considered to be split, to attain the highest accuracy. For the validation averaged across the ten subsets, the correlation coefficient (R^2) and RMSE value between predicted and measured fractal dimension D_f were found to be 0.98 and 0.003, respectively.

Yew et al. has employed the k-Nearest Neighbor (k-NN) model for cultivating waste molasses through the RGB images of *Chlorella vulgaris* to instantly specify the biomass, nitrogen concentration, and pH rather than using time-consuming analytical methods. According to their findings, keeping $k = 4$ (k-nearest neighbors) values in the KNN model reduced the error value by 0.10, close to the actual experimental data. This study has employed the normalized root mean square error (nRMSE) based on the varied k-nearest neighbors to verify the accuracy deviation from the actual data.

Further studies have employed the multivariate Gaussian processes (GP) model for dynamic modeling and optimization of algal production [61]. This study has aimed to introduce an uncertainty term to the GP model that does not need complex kinetic information. The GP has been compared with the ANNs to evaluate their methods based on the real experimental dataset. Moreover, a dynamic optimization with uncertainty has been carried out to prevent over-optimistic optimization beyond the model's validity. When compared against ANNs, the GP has shown excellent predictive performance, and simultaneous uncertainty measures demonstrated a remarkable ability to imitate and optimize complicated biological processes, specifically in cases where the lack of experimental data becomes a severe challenge for the construction of kinetic models.

Mohamed et al. has employed the RSM method to simulate the effect of three parameters such as glucose (organic C source), NaNO₃ (primary N source), and yeast extract (supplementary N, amino acids, and vitamins) on biomass concentration (X_{max}) and lipid yield (P_{max}/X_{max}). In addition, the capability of the RSM method in this study has been evaluated with an ANN approach for anticipating a composition that led to maximum lipid productivity, Pr_{lipid} . The results obtained from a quadratic regression using an RSM model and a Levenberg–Marquardt-trained ANN with ten hidden neurons have been reported as equivalent; however, the ANN yielded higher response output values.

Moreover, this study has employed a statistical test for the importance of the proposed models using the ANOVA method. According to ANOVA analysis, all three different input factors have contributed significantly to the first-order impact on the cell growth model. A feed-forward neural network (FFNN) with backpropagation has been employed for predicting the growth dynamics of the microalga *Karolindinium veneficum* in a culture medium with selected concentrations of the essential nutrients [63]. This study used a three-layer FNN model that sufficiently described the nonlinear relations among a culture medium's nutrients with up to 25 distinct components. In addition, the FNN has been trained to employ the growth dynamics data from over 420 batch culture experiments with various media configurations. Systematic analysis of the FFNN-connected weights partitioning has been determined to distinguish the relative impact of particular nutrients, initial cell concentration, and culture duration on growth profiles. This study has shown that the trained FNN model has accurately predicted cell concentration dynamics in cultures with previously unknown initial conditions, demonstrating an excellent method for predicting growth curves across a broad range of culture conditions.

Noguchi et al. has developed an ANN to predict the growth of polyculture microalgae in an open raceway pond (ORP). The backpropagation algorithm has been used to train a three-layer ANN with eight input parameters, one hidden layer, and one output parameter. By achieving a correlation coefficient between 0.90 and 0.93, the ANN presented in this study has demonstrated an efficient and accurate prediction. Another study has also employed the ANN and a detection method combined with single-excitation fluorescence spectroscopy to monitor and measure microalgae's cell concentration and reduce the measurement cost. The 470 nm light-emitting diode has been used as a light source; data samples with various concentrations of *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* have also been electronically excited. The input and output have a nonlinear connection; therefore, backpropagation with the ANN (BP-ANN) has been optimized by Genetic Algorithms (GA-BP) to estimate the cell concentration. Furthermore, the GA-BP method has been compared with the cell concentration BP-ANN method, and this study has found that the performance of the GA-BP model has attained more accurate results [65].

Susanna et al. has proposed the ANN-based prediction model for the growth of *Spirulina platensis* in a closed reactor. The main objective of this study was to devise a method to enhance *Spirulina* production in photobioreactors by finding a balance between the growth and harvest cycles. Various variables such as culture temperature, light intensity, pH, dissolved oxygen, oxygen production rate, time after harvesting, bicarbonate, phosphate, nitrate, and initial biomass have been used as input parameters. An ANN has been trained with the backpropagation algorithm in a supervised manner. Finally, the results of this study have shown that the proposed ANN could predict *Spirulina* growth for three days beforehand with a coefficient of determination greater than 0.94.

Rogers et al. has employed a transfer learning approach, a category of ML that transmits information from a generalized model to a more domain-specific model for each subject. This study has presented two case studies: biomass growth and lutein production and synthesis, to determine the model's accuracy, reliability, and advantages. Additionally, various transfer learning methodologies, the influence of topology on transfer learning, and the performance of the transfer learning models to baseline kinetic and data-driven models have been discussed. According to their results, transfer learning has been considered the most data-efficient method for predictive modeling of bioprocesses with a classic low-dimensional small dataset problem. Further, the results have suggested that topology substantially impacts the effectiveness of transfer models, giving a window into the underlying process strategies and the information accumulated inside each hidden layer of the reference model.

Several studies have used ANNs to model the growth and accumulation of target metabolites for microalgae over recent years. ANNs are commonly used to model biological systems because of their capability to analyze non-linear relationships between input and output parameters. Therefore, ANN can be used to optimize biological systems.

Liyanarachchi et al. has employed an ANN model with a resilient backpropagation (RPROP) training algorithm as shown in Fig. 4 to simulate the concentrations of total lipid, unsaturated lipid, oleic acid, and biomass of *C. vulgaris* with cultivation time and pH level using input variables. Additionally, this study employed the RSM model to optimize biodiesel production. With $R^2 > 0.97$ for the training dataset and $R^2 > 0.92$ for the validation dataset, the ANN model has strongly correlated with experimental data, exhibiting increased prediction accuracy over Response Surface Methodology (RSM). For the sensitivity analysis, Olden's method has been used to indicate the significance of each input variable on the output variable to achieve higher performance.

According to Olden's plots, this study has found that the effect of pH and time on various metabolites varied; therefore, extra attention should be needed while optimizing *C. vulgaris* growth for biodiesel generation. A multi-objective optimization method and ANN models have also been used to determine biodiesel production's optimal cultivation time and pH.

Fig. 4. Finding optimum cultivation conditions for biodiesel production using Artificial Neural Networks [68].

Table 2

Summary of microalgae growth/biomass prediction using neural-network-based and non-neural-network-based approaches.

Paper	Sources	ML models	Input	Output	Performance
[60]	<i>C.vulgaris</i>	KNN	Initial biomass, nitrogen concentration, and pH value.	Microalgae images for photo-to-property estimation method.	$RMSE = 0.10, 0.11, 0.02$
[57]	Various kinds of microalgae species	AR, DT	Temperature, light intensity, photoperiod, CO_2 content, PO_4 and N concentration, Feed gas flow, CO_2 (feed gas flow).	Algal biomass productivity Lipid content	Recall = 88.5%
[59]	<i>Chlorella sorokiniana</i>	RF	Microalgal floc images	Chord length	$R^2 = 0.98,$ $RMSE = 0.003$
[68]	<i>C.vulgaris</i>	MLP, RSM	pH, and cultivation time.	Biomass, total lipid, unsaturated lipid concentration, and oleic acid concentration	$R^2 = 0.92$ $RMSE = 65.11$
[62]	<i>Tetraselmis sp.</i>	MLP, RSM	Glucose, yeast extract and nitrate concentration.	Biomass concentration and lipid yield	$R^2 = 0.953$ $MAE = 6.048$
[58]	Various microalgal species	LR	Nutrients concentration, biomass production and lipid productivity	TN, TP, COD and Biomass production	$R^2 = 0.985,$ $SSE = 14.352$
[64]	<i>Desmodesmus sp., Scenedesmus sp., Dictyosphaerium sp., Klebsormidium sp., and Micractinium sp.</i>	ANN	Initial microalgae concentration, harvesting period, hydraulic retention time, sodium acetate addition, average solar irradiance, average water temperature, average pH, nitrate concentration	Microalgae concentration in cultivation period	$R^2 = 0.93$
[66]	<i>Spirulina platensis</i>	MLP	Culture temperature, light intensity, pH, dissolved oxygen, oxygen production rate, harvesting time, bicarbonate, phosphate, nitrate, and initial biomass	Trichome concentration, trichome size, and optical density	$R^2 > 0.94$
[65]	<i>C.reinhardtii</i>	ANN, GA	Fluorescence emission spectra	Cell concentration	$R^2 = 0.998$ $MSE = 0.0000998$
[63]	<i>Karlodinium veneficum</i>	FFBN	Initial cell and nutrients concentration and culture duration.	Cell concentration	$R^2 = 0.913$
[67]	Succinic and salicylic acid	Transfer Learning: Compared kinetic and ANN	Light Intensity, nitrate inflow rate, biomass, nitrate, and lutein concentration, salicylic acid concentration	Change in biomass, nitrate, and lutein concentration	Not stated
[27]	<i>C.vulgaris</i>	ANN	Initial concentration of biomass, phosphate, glucose and nitrate, yield coefficients	Change in biomass, phosphate, glucose, and nitrate concentration,	Not stated
[61]	<i>Desmodesmus sp. F51</i>	LR, SGD	Biomass, nitrate and lutein concentration, inflow rate, influent nitrate, light intensity.	Biomass, nitrate concentration, and lutein production.	$GP_{MSE} = 0.024,$ $0.002, 0.064,$ $ANN_{MSE} = 0.011,$ $0.015, 0.011$

The summary of all the ML approaches for the prediction of algal growth with different species, input, output, coefficient of determination (R^2), and RMSE values are stated in Table 2. The results in Table 2 are also visualized in a bar chart in the Appendix. The performance of

ANN and ML models depends on the data, operating conditions, and use case. Therefore, it is difficult to compare the overall performance because the use case and data used or training these models were different. Given that these methods were used for various systems, it is

impossible to deduce any implication of which approach outperforms the other. Given that these methods were used for different systems, it is impossible to deduce any implication of which approach outperforms the other.

4.2. Downstream processing of microalgae processes using ML

4.2.1. Downstream processing of algal cultures using non-neural-network-based approaches

This section overviews different ML approaches for downstream processing of microalgae processes.

Tang et al. has employed ML models such as Random Forest (RF) and Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) for the prediction of yield and hydrogen content of bio-oil (H-bio-oil) based on biomass compositions of feedstock and pyrolysis conditions. Four MLR and RF models have been presented in this study to investigate whether proximal information (i.e., FC-V-Ash) or ultimate information (i.e., CHN-O) was better for predicting bio-oil production and H-bio oil. Four MLR and four RF models have been shown, respectively:

1. Proximate information for predicting bio-oil yield (Proximate-Yield).
2. Ultimate information for predicting bio-oil yield (Ultimate-Yield).
3. Proximate information for predicting H-bio oil (Proximate-H).
4. Ultimate information for predicting H-bio oil (Ultimate-H).

According to this study, MLR performance was insufficient for each model other than RF, which demonstrated that the yield and H-bio oil had no linear relationship with the variables. In this regard, MLR's Ultimate-H has stated a superior performance than others, owing to the restricted linear connection between the hydrogen concentration of biomass feedstock and H-bio oil, supported by the Pearson correlation coefficients (PCC) analysis. On the other hand, the R^2 scores that predicted the bio-oil yield were comparatively better for the RF due to the relatively large datasets. In general, the prediction performance of the RF model with a R^2 score of >0.80 and RMSE score was close to zero.

Sonkar and Mallick has used logistic regression with regularization terms to obtain profitable lipid yields from microalgal biomass for biodiesel purposes by drying the microalgal slurry at various drum surface temperatures (70, 80, 90, and 100 °C) with changing drum speeds (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, and 2.0 rpm). Logistic regression has been employed to classify the residual moisture content range as $<10\%$ (wet biomass) for high lipid recovery with an accuracy of 97%. Compared to bone-dried biomass, drying at 80 °C drum surface temperature with 0.3 rpm has resulted in $>90\%$ lipid recovery based on drying duration, lipid recovery, and energy consumption.

Similarly, Cheng et al. has employed various ML models such as random forest, regression trees, and multiple regression trees to predict product yields and characteristics from hydrothermal treatment (HTT) of multiple feedstocks. The model performance has been incorporated into the life cycle assessment (LCA) model to evaluate two metrics such as net global warming potential (GWP) and energy return on investment (EROI). This study has employed two evaluation metrics, such as R^2 and root mean square error (RMSE), to predict the accuracy of HTT's biocrude yield, hydrochar yield, ACP yield, gas yield, energy, and carbon content of biocrude and hydrochar. The results indicated that the random forest outperformed the regression and multi-linear regression trees.

Further, Mairizal et al. has proposed an ML model such as multiple linear regressions (MLR), to predict biodiesel density, flash point, viscosity, oxidative stability, and higher heating value according to the saponification and iodine value of the feedstock and the content of polyunsaturated fatty acids. The ANOVA method has been employed for each regression to specify the importance of each variable. Finally, the correlation between all the variables has been found by plotting

actual versus predicted data. This study has reported a high prediction performance based on high correlation values for density and higher heating values with prediction errors of less than 5%; on the other hand, outstanding performance for viscosity has been reported with less than 10% error. Similarly, the flashpoint and oxidative stability were predicted with appropriate accuracy with less than 15% error, representing an excellent correlation with saponification, iodine value, and polyunsaturations. Nevertheless, the results of this study demonstrated that other variables could be included and considered to achieve the desired accuracy.

Dahunsi has employed mechanical pretreatment of six distinct lignocelluloses in two separate treatment stages, and their methane output has been predicted using biomass chemical composition. Their study used single and multiple linear regression models to associate biomass chemical composition with methane potentials. The ANOVA method was employed to find the correlation between different chemical compositions of the biomass. The single linear regression model with biomass chemical composition has not attained good performance; however, this model has been considered a time-effective prediction model. On the other hand, a slight change in the prediction accuracy and error has been seen using multiple linear regression. Furthermore, this study employed the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test to obtain the null hypothesis, which used the normal distribution of the residual. This result has shown that the MLR model has attained high accuracy with low error compared to the single regression model.

Ighalo et al. has employed ML models such as linear regression algorithms (LRA), and stochastic gradient descent (SGD) approaches to predict the high heating value (HHV) of biomass. This study has compared the results of both models using different sampling types, such as stratified 10-fold and 20-fold cross-validation and stratified shuffle splits using ten random samples. Their results have shown that the LRA model accuracy has improved during evaluation; however, the SGD model accuracy has dropped. According to this study, carbon from the ultimate analysis, volatile matter from the proximate analysis, and fixed carbon has mainly contributed during model evaluation, which resulted in high biomass heating values. Nevertheless, variables, including ash from the proximate analysis and sulfur from the ultimate analysis, have mainly contributed, resulting in low biomass heating values.

Moreover, the specific growth rate values μ have been reported between 0.3401 ± 0.0001 per day with a doubling time of 2.04 ± 0.01 per day. The prediction results of linear regression analysis have been accomplished by [58], which indicated that COD, TN, and TP concentrations could describe the variability of biomass production with an accuracy of 66.7%, 66.5%, and 66.8% respectively. Liu et al. examined the impacts of influents on organic loading rate and hydraulic retention time (HRT) in a photobioreactor including NSB *R.palustris* chemoheterotrophic bacteria to treat volatile fatty acid wastewater. Additionally, various phases of pollutant removal, biomass production, and carotenoid yield have been analyzed concurrently with functional microbial population dynamics. This study has employed logistic regression using multiple models, including the Luedeking–Piret, to simulate the dynamics of carotenoids from *R.palustris*.

ML methods have recently been employed for bio-oil production with high energy recovery and low nitrogen content using hydrothermal liquefaction of biomass, as shown in Fig. 5 [76]. For bio-oil production, operational conditions, feedstock properties, and phase separation solvents in the hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) method have been employed to predict and optimize bio-oil yield, nitrogen content, and energy recovery. Various ML models, such as Decision Regression Tree, Gradient Boosting Regression, and Random Forest, have been used to enhance bio-oil production while considering associated parameters in HTL. Furthermore, particle swarm optimization (PSO) has been used to drive experimental research to create bio-oil with a high yield and low nitrogen content.

Fig. 5. Bio-oil production prediction using ML to achieve high energy and low nitrogen content [76].

Fig. 6. Optimization of hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) of biomass feedstock.

The analysis of this study has suggested that RF was the best among other ML models for the multi-task prediction of bio-oil yield, yield_{oil}, N_{oil}, and energy recovery ER_{oil} with an average R^2 score > 0.90 for training and $R^2 \sim 0.80$ for the test data. Performance evaluation of the RF model with high multi-task prediction accuracy has been employed to determine feature significance.

Gopirajan et al. has employed the machine-based decision support system (DSS) method as shown in Fig. 6 to optimize the hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) of biomass feedstock. For the training dataset, a Pearson correlation matrix was employed, and bio-oil yield has shown a strong positive correlation between %C, %H of biomass, temperature, and catalyst loading in the HTL process. On the other hand, a negative correlation has been observed between %O, %moisture, and %ash with bio-oil yield. For the validation of DSS performance, this study has performed laboratory experiments and attained an accuracy of 94% using predicted data. The aforementioned ML models, including decision regression tree, RF, and GBR, have been effectively employed for the prediction of biochar yield, nitrogen oil, yield oil, and energy recovery with satisfactory results Li et al.. Nevertheless, prediction accuracy has been insufficient due to the complexity of biomass types and their significant composition divergence.

Pathy et al. has employed eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGB) to predict algal biochar yield along with its composition. This study has implemented a grid search algorithm in the XGB model to analyze all the feasible input variable groups for predicting the biochar yield. In addition to that, this study has exhibited that the H/C, N/C, ash content, pyrolysis temperature, and time were the essential factors for determining the algal biochar yield by employing the grid search method, where H, C, and N were the hydrogen, carbon, and nitrogen content of biomass. The highest regression coefficient R^2 of 0.84 has been achieved for the test dataset between the experimental and model predictive biochar yield. The correlation between biochar production and the input parameters has also been determined using the Pearson correlation coefficient matrix, which indicates that temperature was the most influential element. According to their findings, the proposed XGB model provided significant insights for understanding the effect of input factors on algal biochar production.

However, combining the PCE method with the ensemble method has changed the ensemble model's prediction from deterministic to stochastic, with the effect of process ambiguities illustrated in the form of predictive distributions. This study has attained prediction accuracies of 0.9877, 0.9890, 0.9915, 0.9833, 0.9939, 0.9952, and

Fig. 7. Bio-oil yield prediction using GBR and RF by taking algal compositions and HTL conditions as inputs.

Source: This figure is adapted from the [78].

0.9953 for Methyl-Li, Methyl-M, Methyl-O, Methyl-S, Methyl-P, FAME flow rate, and cetane numbers. Therefore, the results have shown that the proposed model has attained higher prediction performance for predicting the target values and evaluating the influence of process uncertainty.

To attain higher prediction accuracy, Zhang et al. has primarily focused on only one type of biomass (i.e., algae) by employing ML models such as RF and GBR. With algal compositions and HTL conditions as inputs, bio_oil yield (yield_oil), and the amounts of oxygen (O_oil) and nitrogen (N_oil) in bio_oil as outputs. ML models have been used to predict and optimize bio_oil production, as shown in Fig. 7. This study has employed hyperparameter tuning for both models; mainly, two hyperparameters, such as $n_estimators$ and max_depth , have been optimized. When $n_estimators$ were more than 20, and the max depth was less than 10, the average R^2 value of the GBR model achieved satisfactory performance compared to the RF model. Overall, the results have shown that for single and multi-target task prediction, the GBR model with an average test R^2 of 0.90 outperformed RF.

Sultana et al. has employed a Bayesian optimization algorithm (BOA) method with artificial neural network (ANN) and support vector regression (SVR) models as a viable tool for modeling biodiesel synthesis utilizing microalgae oil as feedstock. This study employed hyperparameter tuning with the BOA method to tune the model parameters. Additionally, this study has compared the performance of the proposed hybrid BOA-ANN and BOA-SVR based on various evaluation matrices such as R^2 score, MAE, and RMSE methods with the state-of-the-art models and achieved better performance. Further, the accuracy of the hybrid SVR has been validated by employing additional literature data. Therefore, their study has concluded that the proposed model could allow faster prediction of biodiesel yield from microalgal oil, which may reduce the complexity, cost, and time-consuming laboratory experiments.

The summary of all the non-neural-network-based approaches for the algal downstream processing with different species, input, output, coefficient of determination (R^2), and RMSE values are stated in the table below 3.

4.2.2. Downstream processing of algal cultures using neural-network-based approaches

Morowvat and Ghasemi has employed a feed-forward neural network with a naturally isolated strain of *Chlorella vulgaris* to analyze the effect of three key culture medium constituents on lipid production, such as glucose ($6\text{--}18\text{ g L}^{-1}$), nitrate ($0.5\text{--}4.5\text{ g L}^{-1}$), and phosphate ($0.01\text{--}0.08\text{ g L}^{-1}$) [84]. The significance of the results ($n = 3$) has to be measured using the ANOVA method. This study has considered carbon the most important parameter for lipid synthesis. The optimal medium condition of glucose (15 g L^{-1}), nitrate (1.04 g L^{-1}), and phosphate

(0.31 g L^{-1}) has produced the maximum levels of lipid production (1.944 g L^{-1}) and biomass productivity (0.31 g L^{-1}). The results have demonstrated that using a robust feed-forward ANN model to optimize the medium culture constraints in a mixotrophic culture of *C. vulgaris* for biomass and biodiesel production has been effective.

Chen et al. has employed the ANN method to accurately anticipate the viscosity of microalgae slurry such as *Chlorella pyrenoidosa*. The mass fraction of microalgal cells, shear rate, temperature, and retention time during the hydrothermal hydrolysis process have been employed as input variables, and the microalgal slurry viscosity as the output variable in the ANN model. The predicted ANN model MSE, MAE, and R^2 scores have been reported as 0.725, 0.484, and 0.991, respectively, and showed a strong connection between the experimental and predicted values. Overall, the results have shown that the proposed ANN model has been an outstanding model for calculating the viscosity of the microalgae slurry. Also, ANN has been used to anticipate the weight loss of pure microalgae (M) and peanut shell waste (PS) samples by feeding the heating rates and temperatures [86]. Friedman (FR), Kissinger-Akahira Sunose (KAS), and Flynn-Wall-Ozawa (FWO) are three distinct iso-conversational kinetic models that have also been used to calculate the kinetic and thermodynamic parameters (FWO).

The FWO and the ANN models have been employed, and based on the kinetic model results; the FWO model had the lower variation between the activation energies (E_a) from the experimental data, which has been consistent with the ANN predicted results. Additionally, the dataset specified by the ANN predictions has been determined by estimating the mean square error (MSE) and the regression value (R^2). This study has chosen the optimal values with low MSE and high (R^2) scores to test the accuracy of the data, which indicated a minor cycle error and higher proximity of the predicted output compared to the actual dataset.

Sarkar et al. has examined the yield of chlorophylls and carotenoids from the wet and heat-dried microalgal biomass (isolated *Chlorella thermophila*) using ethanol. In addition, extraction parameters have been optimized, including homogenization time and speed, solvent temperature, solid-solvent ratio, boiling, and microwave time. The extraction process has also been modeled using ANN, which might be beneficial for scaling up the extraction process in the industrial setting. Moreover, the regression coefficient (R), an absolute fraction of variance (R^2), mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), and mean square error (MSE) has been calculated to estimate the prediction efficiency of the proposed ANN model. Finally, the predicted ANN model with six inputs and nine neurons in the one hidden layer has been employed for two outputs, namely chlorophylls and carotenoids, which indicated an R^2 value of 0.9655 and 0.9689, respectively.

The modeling of microalgae flocculation has been investigated by employing various ANN architectures [88]. In this study, microalgae

Table 3
Downstream processing of algal cultures using non-neural-network-based approaches.

Paper	Sources	ML models	Input	Output	Performance
[76]	Food waste, Manure, Sludge, Microalgae, Macroalgae	DRT, GBR, and RF	Elementary composition, the ratio of elementary and biochemical composition, bio-oil yield, O and N content in bio-oil.	Bio-oil yield, nitrogen oil, and energy recovery.	$R^2 = 0.69, 0.75, 0.80, RMSE = 6.17, 5.35, 4.69$
[69]	Herbaceous plant, lignocellulosic plant, and algae.	MLR	Ash, volatile matter, fixed carbon, carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, oxygen, highest treatment temperature, heating rate, particle size, and nitrogen flow rate.	Yield and hydrogen content of bio-oil.	$R^2 = 0.92, 0.87, 0.79. RMSE = 0.84, 3.05, 0.54, 0.56.$
[77]	<i>Scenedesmus obliquus</i> , <i>Cenedesmus abundans</i> , <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> , <i>Sargassum tenerrimum</i> , and <i>Prosopis juliflora</i>	DSS	%C, %H, %N, %O, %moisture, and %ash.	Optimal bio-oil yield, optimization of HHV.	$R^2 = 0.977-0.99.$
[79]	Algal biochar yield	EGB	Algal biomass (C, H ₂ , O, N, H/C, O/C and N/C). Ash, fixed carbon, volatile compound, temperature, heating rate and time).	Biochar yield	$R^2 = 0.84$
[78]	<i>Chlorella</i>	GBR, RF	Elementary compositions, the ratio of elementary and biochemical composition. Bio-oil yield, O and N content in bio-oil.	Bio-oil yield, nitrogen oil, and oxygen content.	$R^2 = 0.96-0.97, RMSE = 2.61, 1.60, 0.68$
[80]	<i>Nannochloropsis oculata</i>	SVM, ANN	Methanol, Nano-catalyst, reaction time, and temperature.	Biodiesel oil yield	$R^2 = 0.963, 0.998, RMSE = 0.0565, 0.0401$
[70]	<i>Chlorella minutissima</i>	LR	Residual moisture content, Lipid yield	Lipid content	Accuracy = 97%
[81]	<i>Euglena gracilis</i>	SVM	Intensity and phase images	Intensity and phase images under the nitrogen-sufficient and nitrogen-deficient conditions	$mAP = 93.30\%, RMSE = 2.15\%$
[82]	Algae, biodegradable organic wastes, Lignocellulosic biomass.	RF	Feedstock compositions, processing conditions, product yield, and characteristics.	Bio-char yield, energy, N and C	$R^2 = 0.85, 0.81, 0.87, 0.78, RMSE = 4, 1, 0.02, 0.002$
[71]	Crops residue, energy crops, biodegradable organic wastes	MLR, DRT, RF	Feedstock compositions, processing conditions, product yield, and characteristics.	Biocrude, hydro char, gas and ACP yield, energy and carbon in biocrude and hydro char	$R^2 = 0.70-0.90, RMSE = 6.42, 6.45, 7.9, 7.9, 4.41, 2.51, 1.70, 0.039$
[72]	Sunflower, peanut, hydrogenated coconut, and hydrogenated copra oil, beef tallow, rapeseed, and walnut oil	MLR	Saponification and iodine value, fatty acids content of feedstock	Viscosity, Density, FP, HHV, and Oxidative stability	$R^2 = 94.1-95.7, RE = 2.7\%, 0.084\%, 1.85\%, 0.61\%, 4.4\%$
[73]	Lignocelluloses biomass, <i>Pennisetum purpureum</i> , <i>Tithonia diversifolia</i> , <i>Chromolaena odorata</i>	LR, MLR	Lignin, arabinan, and protein compositions	Methane yield	$R^2 = 0.55, 0.6300, RMSE = 32, 22 \text{ mL g}^{-1}$
[75]	<i>R.palustris</i>	LR	HRT, Influent COD, OLR, average COD removal, COD removal loading rate, total volatile fatty acids removal, biomass concentration, carotenoid yield, and carotenoid production	COD, TN, TP, biomass production, carotenoid yield	$R^2 = 0.99555, 0.982$
[83]	Wastewater treatment plant	SVM, ANFIS	pH, COD, TS, Free ammonia, Ammonia nitrogen, and Kjeldahl Nitrogen.	Efficiency of WWTP, Prediction of the N removal.	$R^2 = 0.636, 0.72, RMSE = 0.795, 0.232$
[59]	<i>Chlorella sorokiniana</i>	RF	Microalgal floc images	Chord length	$R^2 = 0.98, RMSE = 0.003$

species, i.e., *Chlorella sp.*, have been flocculated with ferric chloride under different circumstances, and the experimental data has been modeled using an ANN method. According to the results of this study, MLP and radial basis function architectures failed to predict the desired outputs successfully; however, modeling has been effective with the ensemble architecture of the MLP network. Therefore, this study has concluded that a combination of best networks, an ensemble ANN, has

achieved the best performance for modeling the *Chlorella sp.* (PTCC 6010) flocculation process with suitable generalization.

Raj et al. used calcium oxide solid nanocatalyst derived from eggshells and *Nannochloropsis salina* to produce biodiesel. The optimization of process parameters for biodiesel production has been investigated using RSM and ANN. Furthermore, the t-test, f-test, and p-value have determined the regression coefficients and significance of

the quadratic response model for biodiesel production. The model's competency has also been checked by analyzing the coefficient of determination (R^2) and adjusted R^2 . In this study, the ANN has been found to be adequate for predicting the precise correlation between the response and significant factors; the high R^2 (0.8751) value has demonstrated that 87.51% of the variance in the entire response could be monitored. The results of this study have shown much less deviation in points between the actual response and predicted values of ANN. Consequently, this study has concluded that the results obtained from the ANN have been highly robust and ideal for prediction and complicated tasks, particularly in the case of biodiesel production.

Further research has been conducted on producing biodiesel from algae oil at lower temperatures and modeling yield and process parameters using RSM and ANN [90]. The ANOVA method has been employed to quantify the experiment's accuracy and the model designed. The accuracy of the RSM and ANN has been determined by approximating the coefficient of determination (R^2) value. The results have shown less deviation between ANN's predicted and actual values than RSM. Additionally, the results have illustrated that ANN outperformed RSM in predictability. In the case of ANN and RSM, a substantial quadratic regression model with R^2 values of 0.99 and 0.96 has been achieved. Similarly, [Vimali et al.](#) has used the RSM on *Desmodesmus sp.* VV2 for biodiesel production with nutrients, stresses, NaNO_3 starvation, CaCl_2 depletion, and magnesium oxide nanoparticle supplementation (MgO). Consequently, the ANN with 11 training methods has been employed to validate RSM results, and it has been found that RSM was more significant. RSM and ANN performance have been compared using RMSE, R^2 and standard error of prediction (SEP). The analysis of this study based on R^2 and RMSE scores has shown that RSM outperformed ANN.

[Srivastava et al.](#) has employed RSM, ANN, and genetic algorithms (GA) to optimize the conversion of microalgae oil to fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) through the use of the supercritical methanol (SCM) transesterification process. Temperature (240 to 300 °C), time (15 to 45 min), and MeOH: oil molar ratio (15 : 1 to 45 : 1) have been chosen as the three process parameters for optimizing SCM transesterification in this study. In addition, preliminary experiments have been carried out by employing a central composite design (CCD) of the RSM-generated matrix, then validated using ANN. The R^2 values for RSM and ANN were 0.97 and 0.99, which exhibited the best model fit to the experimental data. The optimized conditions for FAME conversion efficiency of both predicted models were 98.01% and 98.15%, respectively. An ANOVA analysis has been employed to evaluate the accuracy and significance level of the model. Furthermore, the ANN has been chosen as a more sophisticated optimization method to select the best model based on the minimum RMSE value. According to the comparative analysis of both models, the prediction performance of the ANN for the validation dataset has shown its higher generalization ability for the specified case over the RSM.

The combined impact of a continuous flow microreactor and ultrasonic mixing on transesterification of Aegle Marmelos Correa seed oil employing sodium methoxide catalyst has been investigated by [93]. The RSM approach has been used to investigate the effects of process factors such as flow rate, reaction temperature, catalyst quantity, oil-to-methanol molar ratio, and ultrasonic mixing duration on biodiesel production. The 98% and 91.8% biodiesel yields have been obtained for 0.3 mm and 0.8 mm microreactors. Furthermore, in a 0.3 mm reactor, the highest biodiesel yield has been recorded under the following ideal conditions: 6.8 mL min^{-1} flow rate, 48 °C reaction temperature, 1.3 wt% catalysts, 1:9 oil to methanol molar ratio, and 83 ultrasonic mixing time. In this study, ANN and RSM predictive and generalization capabilities have also been analyzed and compared based on the R^2 score. The predicted R^2 score of both models had been reported as 0.9900 and 0.9955, respectively. On the other hand, the predicted yield of an ANN with a much lower MSE value of 0.00001294 has been found to be lower than RSM.

[Pakalapati et al.](#) has emphasized the optimization of process parameters for synthesizing a biodegradable polymer–polycaprolactone by employing RSM and ANN. The selected input variables were time, temperature, mixing speed, and enzyme-solvent ratios, and the output variable was the polydispersity index. The RSM findings have shown satisfactory performance with a 3.4% variation between predicted and actual values. Further, the ANN has been proposed with five different training algorithms, and the Levenberg–Marquardt training algorithm has been proven to be the best model, with the lowest MSE, MAE, and MAPE scores of 0.10, 0.18, and 0.02, respectively. Both models have been able to predict biopolymer production accurately. RSM has a more significant R^2 and absolute average deviation (AAD) value, demonstrating that RSM outperformed ANN.

[Muhammad et al.](#) has examined modeling and ideal conditions for biodiesel generation from extremely wet microalgae *Chlorella pyrenoidosa* by utilizing the catalyst hydrochloric acid. To optimize individual and interactive effects of parameters such as time (120–240 min), temperature 120–160 °C, solvent-to-wet biomass ratio (2.0–4.674), and hydrochloric acid concentration (2–4 M), three stages of Box–Behnken design response surface methods have been employed in this study. Both ANN and RSM have been trained with Box–Behnken design data to predict responses and design and approximate each model's predictive abilities. The prediction accuracy of both models has been measured using the R^2 score. The results have indicated that the accuracy of both models predicted the experimental data for FAME yields with a high R^2 score of 0.94 and 0.92, respectively.

Furthermore, the RSM and ANN, followed by multiple response optimization with the desirability function method, have been employed individually and concurrently to analyze FAME yield and energy efficiency in the in-situ transesterification process. The design factors for optimizing FAME content and energy efficiencies have included ultrasonic power, reaction duration, methanol, and chloroform concentrations in oil. This study has shown the maximum individual desirability of FAME content to be 87.68%, corresponding to ultrasonic power of 150 W, the reaction time of 100 min, methanol: oil molar ratio of 83, and chloroform: oil molar ratio of 97. The overall desirability has been determined at an ultrasonic power of 137 W, a reaction time of 100 min, and molar ratios of methanol to oil of 83 and chloroform to oil of 30 to achieve FAME content of 81.2% and energy efficiency of 79.8%, respectively, based on simultaneous optimization of energy efficiency and FAME content [96].

The summary of all the neural-network-based approaches for the algal downstream processing with different species, input, output, coefficient of determination (R^2), and RMSE values are stated in [Table 4](#). The results in [Table 4](#) are also visualized in a bar chart in the [Appendix](#). As stated in the earlier section, the performance of ANN and ML models depends on the data, operating conditions, and use case. Therefore, it is difficult to compare the overall performance because the use case and data used or training these models were different. Given that these methods were used for various systems, it is impossible to deduce any implication of which approach outperforms the other. The weaknesses and strengths of all the methods reviewed in this survey paper are discussed in [Table 5](#). Also, the abbreviation of various modeling approaches, inputs, and outputs for various microalgae processes can be seen in [Table 6](#).

5. Challenges and potential solutions for modeling of microalgae cultivation

Data-driven models such as ML algorithms depend heavily on the quality and amount of datasets, which are often limited mainly due to time-intensive data acquisition processes. Moreover, industrial datasets often include significant measurement errors and systematic noises [97]. Additionally, most data-driven models require state variable values at pre-determined time intervals. However, data collected at a plant are frequently acquired at varying time intervals, depending

Table 4
Downstream processing of algal cultures using neural-network-based approaches.

Paper	Sources	ML models	Input	Output	Performance
[84]	<i>C.vulgaris</i>	FFNN	Glucose, nitrate and phosphate	Lipid and biomass concentration.	$mAP = 98.48\%$, 98.33%
[85]	<i>C.pyrenoidosa</i>	ANN	Mass fraction, shear rate, temperature, retention time	Viscosity of microalgae slurry	$MSE = 0.725$, $MAE = 0.48$ $R^2 = 0.991$
[86]	<i>C.vulgaris</i>	ANN	Heating rate, and temperature.	Weight loss	$R^2 = 0.99$ $MSE = 0.00236$
[87]	<i>C.thermophila</i>	FFNN	Homogenization time and speed, solvent temperature, solid-solvent ratio, boiling and microwave time	Chlorophyll and carotenoid yield.	$R^2 = 0.9689$ $MSE = 0.021$, 0.0349
[89]	<i>Nannochloropsis salina</i>	MLP, RSM	Oil to methanol ratio, reaction time and temperature and catalyst concentration	Biodiesel yield %.	$R^2 = 0.875, 0.957$ $RMSE = 0.44$
[90]	<i>C.vulgaris</i>	MLP, RSM	Reaction time, catalyst amount, and Methanol/Oil ratio	Biodiesel yield (%)	$R^2 = 0.99, 0.96$,
[91]	<i>Desmodesmus sp.</i>	MLP, RSM, GA	NaNO ₃ , CaCl ₂ , and MgO,	BP, LP, and LC.	$R^2 = 0.901$
[92]	<i>Chlorella CG12</i>	MLP	Temperature, time, and oil molar ratio	% FAME conversion	$R^2 = 0.97, 0.99$ $RMSE = 1.46, 0.92$
[93]	<i>Aegle Marmelos Correa</i>	ANN	Flow rate, reaction temperature, catalyst amount, oil to methanol molar ratio, and ultrasonic mixing time.	FAME	$R^2 = 0.99$ $RMSE = 0.00001294$
[94]	Caprolactone as monomer Solvent as Toluene	FFNN	Reaction temperature and time, mixing speed, and solvent volume.	Bio-polymer yield.	AAD = 2.45
[95]	<i>C.pyrenoidosa</i>	FFNN	Parameter time, temperature, solvent-to-wet biomass ratio and hydrochloric acid concentration	FAME yield	$R^2 = 0.92, 0.94$ $RMSE = 0.40, 0.38$
[88]	<i>C.vulgaris</i>	MLP	Optical density (OD), pH, and flocculant dosage	Flocculation efficiency	SSE = 0.72 MSE = 0.0347 MAE = 0.1753
[96]	<i>Dry Chlorella sp.</i>	RSM and MLP	Methanol/oil molar ratio, chloroform/oil molar ratio, ultrasonic power, reaction time	FAME yield, energy efficiency	87.6%, 79.8%,

on the efficiency and availability of the analysis equipment. This inconsistency in dataset poses additional challenges such as missing data for data-driven model generation [28]. The latter issues restrict their use of such methods for industrial bio-systems, including algae cultivation applications. Despite the importance of data-driven applications in forecasting unknown dynamic processes for biochemical plants, this aspect has been largely overlooked in the literature, and their applications were restricted only to steady-state operations [97]. Nonetheless, below are proposed solutions for leveraging ML approaches in microalgae cultivation to tackle aforementioned challenges.

5.1. Hurdles and potential solutions for dataset enhancement

In microalgae cultivation processes, control over parameters such as light, temperature, and pH within the reactor is standard practice. However, to comprehensively investigate the impact of parameter variations on microalgal growth and productivity, these parameters must exhibit dynamic changes over time. Employing ML techniques, including DL algorithms, necessitates this dynamic nature of process parameters for effective prediction, monitoring, and optimization. Therefore, to enhance the performance of such algorithms, it is crucial that all process parameters, including light, temperature, pH, dilution rate, and flow rates, exhibit dynamic behavior throughout the cultivation process. In addition, these dynamic process parameters play a crucial role in enhancing the performance of ML algorithms for capturing nonlinear relationships in dynamic systems. By adjusting these parameters in real time, the ML algorithm can better adapt to changing conditions and provide predictive insights for future actions. This dynamic approach enables more accurate modeling of complex processes and facilitates

proactive decision-making as demonstrated by [98]. As mentioned earlier, DL algorithms necessitate extensive datasets to capture the complex relationship between features and responses effectively. However, the conventional practice of taking only one measurement per day from photobioreactors proves insufficient for training deep networks. To address this limitation, it is imperative to adopt a strategy of online sensor measurements considering shorter intervals at a scale of minutes intervals, incorporating varying process parameters to capture the dynamic nature of the process. Recently, new data acquisition techniques have emerged and generated high interest as they generate real-time, high-resolution datasets. Among them, the use of biosensors, which are analytical devices that translate intracellular metabolite concentrations into graded and machine-readable output signals such as fluorescence to facilitate advanced bioanalytical measurements [99,100]. Thus, it has been shown that the advent of ML has enhanced the application of biosensors, making them powerful tools for the improvement of industrially relevant microbial production strains, for example [99,101]. Other approaches for online monitoring of microalgae production have also lately gained attention, such as automated Raman spectroscopy-based sensors and automated flow cytometry, which demonstrated their ability to monitor the physiology of microalgal cells and their intracellular molecules of interest in a complex production environment under different culture conditions at laboratory and industrial algal platforms [102,103]. DL-based data augmentation techniques can be another promising approach to address the scarcity of data in this field. Among different data augmentation techniques, synthetic data can be generated using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Variational Auto Encoders (VAEs). GANs, famous for generating images, have been used recently to generate tabular and time series data. For

Table 5
Strengths and weaknesses of methods reviewed in this survey paper.

Paper	ML/DL model	Strengths	Weaknesses
[57]	Decision tree	Categorize new data accurately	Requires additional training to obtain generalization capability
[58]	Multiple regression	Multivariable regression identified the exact correlation between the input and output responses	Some parameters, such as CO ₂ , did not have a linear correlation with the biomass production
[59]	Random forest	Manage high dimensional input data in a short period	Challenging to create training data
[60]	K-nearest neighbor	Adaptable for estimating the data of biomass, nitrate and pH value with molasses medium through images	Require higher computation cost
[61]	Multivariate Gaussian processes	It can evaluate the relationships by mapping the inputs and outputs using connection weights and bias terms	Optimized model, and overfitting issues
[62]	Response surface method, Artificial neural network	ANN outperformed RSM regarding prediction accuracy. ANN is considered more dynamic in simulating the true behavior of a nonlinear dataset	Limitation of a large dataset
[63]	Feed-forward back-propagation neural network	The FBN showed an outstanding approach for forecasting the growth curves in the range of culture conditions. Highly flexible and adaptable	Environmental factors such as pH, temperature, irradiance, and nutritional factors have not been considered
[64]	Artificial neural network	Achieved higher prediction accuracy and worked well for all the combination of inputs	The dynamic composition of microalgae species and different cultivation methods have not been considered
[66]	Artificial neural network	Capability to predict growth over three days	ANN Model used in this study gave a prediction accuracy of 94% when it was used to predict biomass for one day. However, the prediction accuracy decreased to 90% when it was used to predict biomass for three or four days. The model's prediction accuracy must be improved when predicting biomass over a long period
[67]	Transfer learning	Data efficient for predictive modeling	The model's performance can be improved by modularizing the transfer model and separating domain-specific knowledge from generalizable knowledge. This can be achieved using hybrid models in which a kinetic model simulates known knowledge, and the data-driven model is used to simulate the unknown part
[68]	Artificial neural network	Higher prediction accuracy	The optimum pH range for <i>C. vulgaris</i> relies on cultivation conditions, growth medium, and the microalgal strain. However, the ANN is only pertinent under the specified growth conditions and microalgal strain (<i>C. vulgaris</i>)
[69]	Multiple linear regression, Random forest	RF achieved better performance and accurately identified the complex relationships between the variables and the targets	Linear relationships of bio-oil yield and hydrogen content of bio-oil with input parameters failed to be extracted entirely through multiple linear regression
[70]	Logistic regression	LR perfectly determined the range of the factors required for achieving high lipid yield	Data distribution, and the decision boundary for accurate classification should be known. Multiple experiments are required to identify the correct value of the regularization constant
[71]	Random forest	Appropriate fitting capability	Difficult interpretation
[72]	Multiple linear regression	A simple model with good prediction accuracy	More parameters should have been considered to obtain high prediction accuracy. The study has not considered all the parameters that can interfere with the fuel production process affecting its prediction accuracy using MLR models
[73]	Multiple linear regression	Simple models are used to find the correlation between biomass chemical composition and methane potential	Linear regression achieved a low R^2 score than multiple linear regression. A more complex model could have been used to attain better prediction accuracy
[74]	Linear regression, Scholastic gradient descent	Proposed models accurately captured the linear nature of the carbon-content effect on biomass HHV. ML models with a more mathematical-based learning approach (LRA and SGD) were found to be more appropriate for biomass HHV predictions	The models could not capture the more complex relationship between different parameters, such as sulfur and HHV
[76]	Decision regression tree, Gradient boosting regression, Random forest	Tree algorithms are easier to interpretable and understandable than other black-box algorithms	Datapoints of the dataset did not follow the normal distribution regarding biochemical composition. Ash components of biomass, catalysts, and solvents were not considered for compiling a more comprehensive and sizeable dataset that could have improved the ML prediction performance
[79]	Xtreme gradient boosting	XGB model with four possible input parameters of [ash, fixed carbon, volatile compound, and pyrolysis temperature] predicted the algal biochar yield satisfactorily	The performance of the model could be improved with the acquisition of large datasets on algal biochar composition. Due to the unavailability of sufficient data, the biochemical composition (carbohydrate, protein, and lipids) of algae has not been considered in the present study

(continued on next page)

Table 5 (continued).

Paper	ML/DL model	Strengths	Weaknesses
[78]	Gradient boosting regression	Adaptable for biased datasets	Complex operations
[80]	Artificial neural network, Random forest	Lessen laborious, costly, and time-consuming laboratory experiments	Limited to a few parameters for biodiesel synthesis
[84]	Artificial neural network	Higher prediction accuracy with the best operational conditions for biomass, especially triacylglycerol-rich lipids production	Limited to the simple optimization algorithm
[85]	Artificial neural network	Better explainable capability	Higher computational cost
[86]	Artificial neural network	Higher prediction accuracy and adaptable to complex biomass pyrolysis	Overfitting and overtraining issues
[87]	Artificial neural network	Prediction accuracy was good	Evaluated on a very small dataset with 138 data points. The proposed model should be evaluated on large datasets
[88]	Artificial neural network	Generalizable model with good prediction accuracy	Unable to forecast the targets successfully
[89]	Response surface method, Artificial neural network	ANN is robust and ideal for prediction and complicated problems solving, particularly for biodiesel production	RSM has a low prediction accuracy and a high deviation of points between the actual and predicted data
[90]	Response surface method, Artificial neural network	Higher prediction performance and correlation coefficient for ANN	Though ANN gave better performance, but the optimized value of biodiesel yield was higher for RSM. ANN could have been optimized to obtain a higher value of biodiesel yield
[91]	Response surface method, Artificial neural network	Prediction accuracy was good	Evaluated on only 27 data points
[92]	Response surface method, Artificial neural network, Genetic algorithm	High prediction ability	RSM and ANN are associated with problems such as local convergence of generalization and prediction
[93]	Response surface method, Artificial neural network	Prediction accuracy was good	RSM is capable of capturing linear functions, but it is challenging to overcome ANN's advantages in capturing non-linearity.
[94]	Response surface method, Artificial neural network	Both models accurately predicted the biopolymer yield	Twenty-five data samples were used; therefore, ANN's performance was lower than RSM's
[95]	Response surface method, Artificial neural network	Both ANN and RSM predicted the experimental data for fatty acid methyl ester yields with high correlation coefficients	Evaluated on only 29 data points. RSM is unable to capture the nonlinearity
[96]	Response surface method, Artificial neural network	Both models successfully predicted the desired variables for biodiesel production and exergy efficiency of the in-situ transesterification	High levels of methanol and chloroform in the oil increased waste, which led to additional exergy degradation. In addition, more energy and exergy are needed to retrieve excess solvents and decompose FAME downstream

example, [Lyu et al.](#) employed VAE to generate synthetic data for areas where data availability is scarce to improve the effectiveness of process monitoring. Due to the limited amount of data in such regions, training the VAE model extensively becomes necessary. Consequently, process data from other regions are incorporated to supplement the insufficient information in the dataset of the scarce region. Furthermore, in transfer learning, data augmentation for time series, such as time-warping window slicing, time series interpolation, seasonal decomposition, and rolling window statistics, can be applied to increase the adequate size of the target dataset artificially. This is especially useful when the available data is limited, as these approaches introduce variations in the input data and help the model generalize better [105]. [Zhang et al.](#) proposed an innovative approach, incorporating transfer learning with the transformer model to forecast the outcomes of the Baeyer-Villiger reaction, a characteristic reaction dataset with limited data points. The results of this study illustrate that integrating a transfer learning approach significantly enhances the accuracy of the transformer-transfer learning model compared to the transformer-baseline model.

5.2. Potential solutions for modeling rigorousness enhancement

A hybrid semi-parametric modeling framework has been proposed in the literature that employs the advantages of physics-based and data-driven approaches and can be easily incorporated into various online optimization techniques to lessen the restrictions of physics-based and

data-driven models and promote their application to industrial bioprocesses. Furthermore, the hybrid semi-parametric modeling method is considered a practical approach in determining possible problems correlated with optimizing industrial biosystems, such as the low quality and quantity of datasets, lack of physical knowledge of the process, on-line measurements, and the high cost of periodic sampling. Therefore, some solutions regarding modeling approaches have been presented in the following section.

6. Significance of hybrid modeling approaches

In recent years, hybrid semi-parametric modeling, as a third modeling approach has been proposed to balance the advantages of physics and data-driven-based modeling approaches [107]. This approach integrates non-parametric (black-box) and parametric (white-box) into a hybrid semi-parametric model system to benefit from mechanistic and data-driven models. A hybrid model's structure is adaptable, for instance, a series or parallel network, and is characterized by accumulating accessible process data and physical information as shown in [Fig. 8](#) [108]. If a process model (white box) is available, the parallel structure depicted in [Fig. 8A](#) is commonly used; nevertheless, the performance of this kind of structure is restricted owing to unmodeled effects, nonlinearities, and dynamic behavior. The black box model can map the differences between experimental and white box model predictions in a parallel structure so that the mechanistic model outputs

Fig. 8. Different structures used for training Hybrid models. A indicates the parallel configuration and B and C indicate the serial configuration.

can be adjusted for future forecasting or to consider the unspecified dynamics in numerical integration [109].

In the series configuration, the white box illustrates a model derived from first principles such as conservation laws, energy balances, momentum, impulse, and population derived from the process. The black box generally reflects the underlying transport terms or kinetics since it is crucial to construct a generally accurate model representation at a reasonable cost [108]. This series configuration Fig. 8B is beneficial when there is no accurate information about underlying processes; however, enough process data exists to deduce the unknown patterns. To precisely project the production rates of biochemical species, a feed-forward single hidden layer ANN was used in conjunction with a serial mechanistic model to simulate the fed-batch cell culture process data set [110]. The author demonstrated an excellent prediction performance of titer as compared to statistical predictive models.

The series configuration Fig. 8C may be employed to connect the process state and particular process characterizing parameters as an alternative to the parallel structure, such as when white-box model predictions are used as inputs to a nonparametric model. For instance, the serial hybrid modeling that contained ANN was employed by [28] to identify control actions and predict future behaviors for bioprocess online simulation and optimization. This study showed that a serial hybrid modeling framework could determine practical issues, namely low quality and quantity of collected data and lack of physical knowledge of processes.

6.1. Hybrid modeling applications in chemical engineering

Hybrid semi-parametric modeling has been employed in numerous chemical engineering applications, such as polymerization processes [111], crystallization [112], distillation columns [113], metallurgical processes [114], chemical reactors [115], mechanical reactors [116], and drying processes [117]. Furthermore, hybrid semi-parametric modeling has been used in biochemical engineering, for instance, for the modeling of fungi cultivation [117], for the modeling of yeast fermentation [118], for the modeling of mammalian cell cultivations [119], for modeling of hybridoma cell cultivations [120], for the modeling of insect cell cultivations [121], and for modeling the counter-ion fluxes across an ion-exchange membrane in a membrane-supported biofilm reactor [122].

Similarly, hybrid semi-parametric modeling has been employed to predict, monitor, optimize, and control microalgal processes. Zhang et al. has employed an automated model structure method that includes model reformulation and sparse optimization. In this model, binary variables have been added to the hybrid model; later, this model was reconstructed as a mixed-integer nonlinear programming (MINLP) problem. In the next stage, after the model reconstruction, this study used sparse optimization to find the possible kinetic model structure and the fewest polynomial terms that sufficiently fit the several created datasets. This study has suggested that employing the automated model structure identification framework allows the creation of a hybrid model that incorporates physical knowledge and ML approaches.

6.2. Hybrid modeling approaches for microalgae processes

Zhang et al. has presented a novel hybrid semi-parametric modeling framework for bioprocess online monitoring, prediction, and optimization that integrates physics-based and data-driven models. Because of its high complexity and growing market need, algal lutein synthesis has been used as the case study in this study. The hybrid structure employed in this study first created high-quality data by reducing noise from the original measurements using a kinetic model, and then the ANN was used to anticipate the optimal control actions. The continuous future process trajectories have been shown by refitting the basic kinetic model with the data-driven model to predict discrete future data points, allowing for accurate process monitoring at any operating time. The results have shown that the problems associated with optimizing industrial biosystems can be handled using a hybrid modeling approach. Industrializing microalgae-based bio-renewables necessitates the identification of appropriate photobioreactor designs and process operating conditions.

As a result, del Rio-Chanona et al. has developed a novel data-driven surrogate modeling approach that uses a state-of-the-art deep learning method to reduce the computational time from months to days. This study has developed and integrated computational fluid dynamics (CFD) with a kinetic model to evaluate PBR hydrodynamics and bioprocess kinetic behaviors. Both models have been combined to train a CNN. Furthermore, a hybrid stochastic optimization method has been developed in this study to optimize the Photobioreactor (PBR) designs and culture conditions for biomass growth and bioproduct synthesis. The results have indicated that the proposed framework, which has integrated exceptional predictive power with excellent computational efficiency, was appropriate for biosystem modeling and optimization. However, due to complex biological behavior, a hybrid modeling strategy has not been commonly used for microalgal processes. Moreover, the amount of information-rich data is a big challenge for training machine or deep learning models for better predictions. Further development could be possible for algal photo production if the challenges related to data and modeling approaches are resolved to achieve better predictions and interpretability.

7. Conclusion

The main focus of this paper was to provide a comprehensive review of various ML algorithms employed for monitoring, prediction, and optimization algae cultivation processes. The predictive performance of these techniques is significantly influenced by the size of the datasets; larger datasets often tend to yield superior prediction performance for both neural and non-neural ML models. However, data collection in bioprocesses, including algae cultivation, presents significant challenges. Therefore, large training datasets for this purpose are often rare, mainly due to the time-intensive data acquisition process. Gathering data from various sensors at an industrial scale introduces complexities,

often resulting in systematic errors and noise in the acquired data. Moreover, continuously monitoring all state variables, such as biomass content, throughout the operation proves impractical. Furthermore, data collected at a plant are often acquired at varying time intervals depending on the efficiency and availability of the analysis equipment. This irregularity introduces additional difficulties such as missing data. However, most data-driven models compute state variable values at fixed time intervals. Consequently, the application of ML methods in algal cultivation processes, akin to other bioprocesses, remains constrained by these limitations. In the final section of the paper, we highlighted potential solutions for data quantity and quality enhancement using advanced online monitoring techniques for data acquisition and new widely adopted methodologies for data augmentation.

8. Future directions

While ML models lack inherent understanding of the underlying physics of algal cultivation processes, mechanistic or kinetic models excel in this aspect but often fall short in prediction accuracy due to oversimplified representations. A hybrid learning approach, merging the strengths of ML and physics-based models, offers a promising solution. By combining these approaches, the limitations of each can be mitigated, leading to more accurate predictions, improved extrapolation capabilities, enhanced interpretability and reduced data requirement in modeling. As discussed in this paper for fully data-driven models, the data quality and quantity still plays a pivotal role also for enhancing the predictive capabilities of hybrid models. Various filtering techniques, including Gaussian filters, can effectively mitigate noise and errors within the data. Moreover, addressing missing values is crucial, and methodologies such as imputation with statistical metrics like mean, median, or through more sophisticated techniques outlined in [124] provides the overview of simple imputations, regression imputations, hot-deck imputations, expectation-maximization, multiple imputations, and imputation methods inspired by ML to handle the missing data value in datasets. These techniques help improve the prediction performance of microalgae growth and productivity. Moreover, data augmentation through methods like GANs and Autoencoders can be employed. However, caution must be exercised in generating synthetic data to ensure it accurately represents the characteristics of real data, as noted in [125]. Biases in synthetic data generation can adversely affect prediction performance when models are trained on both real and synthetic data [125].

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tehreem Syed: Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Felix Krujatz:** Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Yob Ihadjadene:** Writing – review & editing. **Gunnar Mühlstädt:** Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing. **Homa Hamedi:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Jonathan Mädler:** Conceptualization, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Leon Urbas:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Appendix

Abbreviations used in this paper are given in Table 4. The bar chart shows the performance comparison of various non-neural and neural-network-based ML approaches for predicting microalgae growth and downstream processing of algal cultures (see Figs. 9 and 10).

Table 6
Abbreviation of modeling approaches, input, and outputs for various microalgae processes.

Abbreviation	Nomenclature
AAD	Absolute Average Deviation
AR	Association Rule
ANN	Artificial Neural Networks
AMT	Alternating Model Tree
ANFIS	Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System
BR	Bayesian Regularization Propagation (Bayesian regularization)
BFGS	Quasi-Newton and One Step Secant
COD	Chemical Oxygen demand
C, H ₂ , N, O	Carbon, Hydrogen, Nitrogen, and Oxygen
DRT	Decision Regression Tree
DSS	Decision Support System
DT	Decision Tree
DO	Dissolved Oxygen
dt	Doubling Time
EGB	Extreme Gradient Boosting
EC	Electrical conductivity
FAME	Fatty Acid Methyl Ester
FP	Flash Point
FC	Fixed Carbon
FFNN	Feed-Forward Neural Network
FBN	Feed-forward backpropagation neural network
GBR	Gradient Boosting Regression
GP	Gaussian Processes
GA	Genetic Algorithm
GDX	Gradient Descent
HHV	Hydrothermal Liquefaction of Biomass
HHV	Higher Heating Value
HRT	High Reaction Time
IC	Initial Concentration
IAI	Integrated Assessment Indices
KNN	K-Nearest Neighbor
LMS	Least Median Square
LP, LC, BP	Lipid Productivity, Biomass Productivity, Lipid Content
MLR	Multiple Linear Regression
MLPR	Multi-Layer Perceptron Regressor
mAP	Mean Average Precision
Methyl O	Oleic Acid Methyl Ester
Methyl P	Palmitic Acid Methyl Ester
Methyl M	Myristic Acid Methyl Ester
Methyl Li	Linoleic Acid Methyl Ester
Methyl S	Stearic Acid Methyl Ester
MSE	Mean Square Error
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
NLR	Non-linear Regression
NN	Neural Network
OLR	Organic loading rates
OSS	One Step Secant
PCE	Polynomial Chaos Expansion
RF	Random Forest
RE	Average Relative Error

(continued on next page)

Fig. 9. Performance comparison of ML models for microalgae growth prediction. Overall, ANN achieved the highest prediction performance in [65].

Fig. 10. Performance comparison of ANN and ML models for downstream processing of algal cultures.

Table 6 (continued).

Abbreviation	Nomenclature
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
SVM	Support Vector Machines
SGD	Stochastic Gradient Decent
SEE	Standard Error of Estimate
SEP	Standard Error of Prediction
TN, TP	Total Nitrogen, Phosphorus
TS	Total Solids
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant

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